

An Exploration of the Impact that Continuous, Summative Assessment has on how University Mathematics Students Spend their Study Time

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A move to modularisation has seen an increase in the amount of continuous, summative assessments undergraduate students must complete. Students advocate for these assessments as it encourages them to remain engaged, and lecturers feel compelled to give them to ensure students do not neglect their modules. This phenomenon has been dubbed “the assessment arms race”. In this study we examine the impact that continuous, summative assessment has on how Stage 3 mathematics undergraduate students in University College Dublin choose to spend their study time. Students completed weekly timesheets reporting how much time they spent on activities in their six modules in trimester 2, 2019-20. They were asked to describe the factors that influenced how they spent their study time, and if there were other activities they would have liked to complete. Although data collection was cut short owing to COVID-19, an analysis of the data up to that point provides clear evidence of the assessment arms race in action and highlights the behavioural impact that it has on how students approach their learning. We examine recommendations, and discuss possible solutions, to address this.

Introduction

In all arms races, all players can be harmed because they need to take actions they would not otherwise choose. If this holds for the assessment arms race, then there are no winners, only losers (Harland, 2020, p. 18).

As Head of Teaching and Learning in the School of Mathematics and Statistics, the second author received feedback from undergraduate mathematics students about an excessive workload caused by in-trimester summative assessments. With a usual registration of six, 5-credit European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS) credits per trimester, students claimed to experience weeks when the number of assignments due, and tests scheduled, resulted in an unmanageable workload. Anecdotally, students were not advocating for a great reduction in assessments and did not want 100% final examinations. Along with many lecturers, students felt that what was needed was better coordination of the timings of tests and assignments. This task fell to Programme Directors whose attempts to coordinate the scheduling were mainly unsuccessful. The flexibility of the modular system meant that students enrolled on a programme were frequently not taking the same six modules. In turn, module coordinators could argue that there were pedagogical reasons for the frequency and timing of their assessments, and if they reduced the number of assessments dramatically, students might end up ignoring their module.

This phenomenon University College Dublin (UCD) is experiencing is not unique. Studies conducted in Ireland (National Forum, 2016; O’Neill, 2019), the UK (Tomas & Jessop, 2019), and New Zealand (Harland et al., 2015) describe high levels of continuous, summative assessment in university undergraduate programmes, caused or exacerbated by a modular system – aptly called “the assessment arms race” by Harland et al. (2015). The authors of these studies call for universities to take a programmatic approach to assessment in

order to promote deep learning and “slow scholarship” (Harland et al., 2015, p. 536). However, to do this requires a re-think of our programmes, and we wanted more than anecdotal evidence before embarking on such a change. Our aim in conducting this study was to obtain an evidenced-based, programmatic view of continuous, summative assessment in our school, and its impact on student study behaviour, in order to start a conversation amongst faculty. Specifically, we aimed to address the following research questions: How much time do students self-report spending on each module activity each week of the trimester? What factors influence students’ choices of how much time to spend on each module activity each week of the trimester? What module activities do students report wanting to spend more time on each week of the trimester?

To this end, in Trimester 2 of 2019-20, we recruited students from one of our undergraduate programmes to complete a weekly timesheet for the duration of the trimester. Unfortunately, the pandemic forced us to pivot online after seven weeks. Ultimately, student participation in the study was negatively affected and we did not collect data after week 11. In this paper we present the findings from the analysis of the data gathered until UCD pivoted online and examine implications for mathematics programme outcomes and design.

Literature Review

Harland et al. (2015) conducted in-depth interviews probing assessment practices at a university in New Zealand, with 62 lecturers and students from the Science, Humanities, and Professional disciplines. Irrespective of the discipline, they found that students preferred small continuous, summative assessments as opposed to high-stakes final examinations. The students reported that they had no time to work on non-graded work, and sometimes missed lectures and/or worked in groups to complete assignments or study. High-achieving students felt they were always working at sub-optimal levels, which created stress. Overall students exhibited a “love-hate relationship” (p. 535) towards assessment as they were stressed by the frequency of it and frustrated by the lack of coordination amongst lecturers. Lecturers were unhappy about assessing frequently, but the flexibility afforded by the modular system meant that if they did not, students may ignore their modules. This left them competing for students’ attention and exercising what Harland et al. call a “pedagogy of control” (p. 538).

Tomas and Jessop (2018) compared programme assessment data from 73 programmes across 35 research-intensive and 38 teaching-intensive universities in the UK. They found that the research-intensive universities had significantly higher summative assessment loads, and significantly more assessment by examination than the teaching-intensive institutions. They cite an example of a 3-year mathematics programme in a research-intensive university that had 227 summative assessments. They conjecture that with this level of frequency, the assessments must be relatively brief and question whether such tasks can encourage deep learning. The 16 Science students in the Harland et al. (2015) study reported having on average 1.44 graded assessments per week, with a module load of up to four modules per semester. A study of assessment practices in third-level programmes in Ireland (National Forum, 2016) found that in single-trimester modules, the average number of assessments was

2.6 and 4.5 for five and ten ECTS credits module respectively. This averages to 1.04 and 0.9 weekly assessments respectively. They found the most common module size in Ireland was 5 ECTS credits meaning that students may be taking up to six modules per semester.

All learning takes time, and when students are constantly being assessed, it is questionable whether they have the time and space needed to engage in deep learning and develop higher order skills (Harland et al., 2015; Tomas & Jessop, 2018) and have the opportunity to become self-directed and independent learners (Harland et al., 2018). The authors of the UK and New Zealand studies, along with O’Neill (2019) in Ireland, all advocate taking a programmatic approach to assessment – for example by assessing across the curriculum and focusing on programme outcomes. Harland and Wald (2020) provide further suggestions for “de-escalating” the arms-race. To address the scheduling issue, they observe that it may be necessary to reduce student choice in modules, and note that if workload is still an issue, then lecturers need to assess only that which they deem important. They acknowledge that this “will require careful planning and systemic change over time” (p. 10), while O’Neill (2019) observes that lecturers seem unwilling to move from the status-quo.

Method

For this study, an undergraduate mathematics student cohort was required that was enrolled to a suite of core modules in trimester 2, ensuring a level of homogeneity among participants. We also required that the group was sufficiently large to recruit participants from. Finally, in UCD, Science students choose their degree pathway at the end of their second year, therefore we were looking for students in Stages 3 or 4. Subsequently, the participants chosen for this study were Stage 3 undergraduate students (n=20) pursuing a single major in Applied and Computational Mathematics (ACM). This cohort was chosen as they have five core modules in trimester 2 of Stage 3. The sixth module is an elective. The third author was Programme Director for this group. While he was responsible for recruiting participants initially, the first author was responsible for contact with them after recruitment, and anonymising data as she was based outside of the School of Mathematics and Statistics and had no academic relationship, or otherwise, with the students. This allowed participants to remain anonymous to the other authors who held the previously mentioned support roles in the school. In total, nine students agreed to participate (45% response rate).

As we were keen for participants to remain engaged for a trimester, we had to strike a balance between the level of detail required of them, and the time it would take them to record it. Consequently, we asked participants to complete a spreadsheet provided on Google Drive at the end of each week, starting in week 2, indicating the hours spent on a list of activities across each of their six modules. The list of module activities was devised by the authors and was adapted over the first two weeks of the study as students described additional activities engaged in. The final list is as follows: lectures; tutorials; assignment; revising for test; reviewing lecture notes; and revising for final exam. We note that marks were not awarded for lecture attendance. For each module, participants were asked to provide open responses on the spreadsheet, describing the main factors influencing their study time and stating any activities

they would have liked to spend more time on. While this is a quantitative study, the open responses allowed students to describe their decisions for the time they reported spending on each weekly activity. To incentivise consistent participation, any participant who completed the timesheet for a given week, was entered into a weekly draw for a €20 *One4All* voucher. If participants did not complete the sheet for a week, the draw was intended as an incentive to re-engage with the study, and a participant could win the draw multiple times. We planned to seek more in-depth explanations from students through interviews at the end of the trimester. However, this part of the study was impacted by the disruption caused by COVID-19.

The response rate varied each week from between one and eight students. The decision was taken to suspend data collection after week 11 of the trimester – the penultimate week of lectures. Only one student completed the spreadsheet in Weeks 10 and 11, therefore we will only include data collected up to Week 9 in what follows. Descriptive statistics were performed on the weekly time data and the average weekly time spent on each activity was calculated (RQ1). This was then compared with an assessment calendar, the students’ comments on what influenced how they spent their time each week (RQ2) and what they would have liked to spend more time on (RQ3). UCD entered lockdown during the field-work break (two weeks when classes are not scheduled) when seven weeks of the trimester had been completed. Although the data collection was cut short, the results up to this first field-work break shed light on how students spend their study time, and their motivations for doing so. This period also includes the traditional midterm assessments. We will present our findings in the next section.

Results

The weekly participation rates in the study and the average time students self-reported studying each week are presented in Table 1. The study commenced in Week 2 and FW1 and FW2 denote two field-work break weeks when none of the core modules had scheduled lectures or tutorials. Of the nine participants, eight completed the spreadsheet in Weeks 4-6, with seven taking part in Week 7. The average time spent per week from Weeks 2-9 (including FW1 and FW2) ranged from 29 hours to 46 hours.

Table 1

Number of participants and average time spent studying each week

	Wk2	Wk3	Wk4	Wk5	Wk6	Wk7	FW1	FW2	Wk8	Wk9
Students	4	5	8	8	8	7	6	4	4	3
Av. Time	29	37	34	42	34	39	15	27	46	46

In terms of the first research question, the average time students self-report spending weekly on each module activity is presented in Figure 1. We address the second and third research questions by examining these results in conjunction with the assessment calendar for

the five core modules (Table 2), and the student comments on the factors that impacted how they chose to spend their time and the activities they would like to have spent more time on.

There were no assignments due, or tests scheduled in Week 2, and the three activities that students spent most time on were attending lectures, doing assignments, and reviewing lecture notes. In Week 3, Module D had an assignment worth 7% due and all four participants that week stated that they spent time on this assignment. Two students noted that they worked on other assignments also - one due in week 4, and to prepare for the tests in Weeks 4 and 5. In terms of what they would have liked to spend more time on, two students in each of Weeks 2 and 3 mentioned that they would have liked to spend a little more time (1-2 hours) on some of the “ungraded” worksheets and reviewing or pre-viewing lecture notes.

Figure 1

The average proportion of time spent by students on each academic activity over the trimester and the average number of hours for each week are displayed at the top of the bar.

Attending lectures remains the activity with the highest proportion of time spent on it in Weeks 3 and 4 at 40.5% and 36.4% respectively. In Week 4, revising for a test is the next most popular activity at 30.8%. All participants said that the test in Module D influenced how they spent their time. Two commented that they spent time revising for upcoming tests in Week 5 also. Indeed Week 5 saw tests scheduled in three modules and the proportion of time students reported spending revising for tests increased to 54.5%. All seven participants commented on how the tests dominated how they spent their time, with two noting that it impacted on lecture attendance.

Multiple in class tests meant I didn't have time to catch up on lecture notes and also affected my attendance in lectures. [Student 8, Week 5]

The midterms influenced basically what I was doing during the week. As soon as one was over, I was preparing for the next one. [...] I skipped a few lectures this week so that I could study for midterms during the week. Wish I could have went. I don't think it's valuable to go to lectures when midterms are on. [Student 5, Week 5]

The two core modules that did not have summative assessments in Week 5 were Modules D and E. Three of the participants stated that they would have liked to have spent time revising notes and doing "ungraded" assignments for Module E. One student skipped lectures in Module D to work on the assessments due, with another stating they would have liked to have had time to review the notes for this module in order not to fall behind.

Table 2

Timings of assessments due and tests scheduled with corresponding weightings

	Module A	Module B	Module C	Module D	Module E
Week 3				Assign. (7%)	
Week 4		Assign. (5%)		Test (10%)	
Week 5	Test (10%)	Test (7.5%)	Test (15%)		
Week 6					
Week 7		Assign. (5%)		Assign. (7%)	Test (20%)
FW1					Assign. (5%)
FW2					
Week 8	Test (20%)		MCQ (15%)		
Week 9		Assign. (10%)	Assign. (10%)		

There were no assessments due or scheduled in Week 6, but five of the six participants stated that the upcoming assessments in Week 7 influenced how they spent their time. The other student was sick for the week. The choice of which of the three assessments to concentrate on in Week 6 was an issue for some of the participants.

[Module E] midterm worth 20% next week so most of my time was spent on that. That meant I had to neglect the [Module B] and [Module C] assignments which are due next week because they are worth more [sic]. [Student 9, Week 6]

Student 1 also spent "a lot of time" studying Module E, whereas Student 5 concentrated on the assignments but then stated that they would have liked to have spent more time revising Module E. Students 6 and 9 stated they would have liked to have spent 11 and 13.5 hours more respectively on the three assessments. Modules A and C did not have assessments scheduled for Week 7. Student 9 would have liked to work on "non-graded problem sheets"

for Module C, while another student would have liked to pre-read lecture notes in it. Student 8 would have liked to have had time to review the lecture notes for Module A.

Unsurprisingly, Week 7 was dominated by the three assessments and students reported spending on average 24.7 hours, or 63.5% of their time, revising for the test or working on assignments.

No time for going to lectures or studying modules other than the ones with all of the assignments and midterms due. [Student 1, Week 7].

The first field-work break was welcomed as a time to take a break, although one student spent it applying for internships and doing interview preparation. Indeed, while summative assessment deadlines heavily impacted how students spent their time during the trimester, students also reported that their schedules were impacted by being sick, completing short-courses, undertaking competitions, writing internship applications, preparing for and attending interviews, and of course later in the trimester by COVID-19.

Finally, some general comments about the module activities listed in the study. One student stated that the activity 'Reviewing lecture notes' is often part of completing an assignment. And revising for a test may include completing non-graded assignments:

Primarily [worked on] graded assignments ensuring all answers were correct but I also spent notable amounts of time on nongraded assignments in preparation for the numerous midterm exams I will have over week 4 and 5. [Student 4, Week 3]

This comment was made in the third week of the trimester when students had more time to plan. From comments in later weeks we can surmise that as assessments became more frequent, notes were reviewed and assignments completed on a need-to-do basis.

Discussion and Conclusion

The findings show that as early as Week 4, summative assessments are playing a role in students' decisions on how to spend their study time. In Weeks 5-7, revising for tests or completing graded assignments dominates, and comes at the cost of missing lectures and ignoring other modules. This resonates with findings on one of the student assessment experiences reported by Harland et al. (2015). Students reported not having time to work on study activities outside those that were graded and reported missing lectures to cope with the workload. High-achieving students always felt like they were under-achieving and were experiencing stress as a result. In the open comments, some of our students did speak about an assessment being "very stressful because it was worth so much" or noting that "not much due this week so I wasn't so stressed". Given that the amount of extra time students reported wanting to spend on assessment activities increased during the trimester, it may indicate that they felt they were not performing at their best.

A weakness of this study is not having a complete set of data for the trimester nor having student interviews to expand on the data more. Nonetheless, we can see the assessment arms race in action from the student perspective. We are missing the lecturer perspective, although we suspect it would be similar to that of the lecturers in the Harland et al. (2015) study. We can see that lecturers' concerns about students ignoring their module if it is not

assessed, are well-founded. We also did not seek evidence of whether the students were engaging in deep learning and developing higher order skills (Harland et al., 2015; Tomas & Jessop, 2018) given their assessment loads.

We are at the start of the journey to address what we believe is an “assessment arms race” in our undergraduate programmes, and we want to proceed quickly, but with caution. There are often many off-the-cuff suggestions when this problem is raised: only allow final exams; decree that all modules should have only one continuous summative assessment item, along with a final examination, and that the assessments be coordinated at the programme level (if this was even possible to arrange in a modular system) et cetera. However, the consequences of these decisions need to be considered. Like the authors of the studies mentioned above, we see possible solutions including some, or all, of the following: an elimination, or reduction, of student module choice; a reduction in the number of 5-credit modules; and/or, take a programmatic approach to assessment that ensures students meet high-level programme outcomes. An example of such a programmatic approach in an undergraduate ecology degree is provided by Harland (2020) where a research-based approach is taken. We suspect we are not unique across the Higher Education system in Ireland and look forward to conversations with colleagues at MEI to discuss this further.

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